

A Study on Educational Contribution of the Arya Samaj in India

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ABSTRACT

When the spread of materialistic ideology has contributed to undermine the sense of eternal values; when the very existence of Bharatvarsha', the land of Philosophers, Rishis and Educationists has been threatened by alien powers, there is no need to argue that Education for reconstruction, National and International unity must be based on sound philosophy which seeks transform the brute man into man the good, and which strengthens the national and international unity. We find a burning torch to the deep darkness and that is in Swami Dayanand Saraswati. Though Brahma Samaj and Prarthana Samaj did much to eradicate the social evils yet their sphere was limited. They had no influence outside the provision of their birth. They possessed no adequate knowledge of their influence was limited only up to the upper strata of the society.

Introduction: -

The 19th century is one of the most eventful and formative periods of the history of India. In fact, it was the period that saw the birth of modern India and the beginning of a series of thoughts and movements of far reaching consequences. It is a well-known maxim that the deepest darkness precedes the brightest dawn and of this the glowing history of 19th century India provides an admirably eloquent example. Actually the 18th century, particularly the later half of it, was one of the darkest ages in the long and eventful history of India. A survey of the religious condition of that age is necessary to understand thoroughly the development of the 19th century in a proper historical perspective.

The religious conditions in India at that time when Dayanand was touring the country, were not satisfactory. The Vedas, though recognised as 'Divine Revelation' by all Hindus, were read by none. Indeed, they had become sealed books and even the Sanskrit scholars had forgotten the Vedic philosophy. The rulers of several native states, i.e. Banaras and Udaipur were ignorant of Sanskrit and had to trust the pundits. They were guided by preconceived notions and did not possess an open mind to cherish new ideas. The condition of Hindu pundits was far from satisfactory. They were greedy and could indulge any literacy fraud for some pecuniary gain. The pundits read Bhagwat and Puranas which, according to Dayananda were the root cause of all the religious and social evils in the country. Hinduism was attacked by aggressive Islam and Christianity. The Hindus tried to meet them on their own ground.

Brahmo Samaj, which was established by Raja Rammohun Roy in 1830 was the only society functioning them for the amelioration of the people. Earlier Rammohun Roy fought against the Hindu orthodoxy. These conditions were minutely observed by Dayananda, and were responsible for the evolution of his religious ideas. Dayananda was quite unhappy with the existing attempts at reform and criticised Brahmo Samaj as too much westernised and cut off from indigenous roots.

Foundation of The Arya Samaj: -

The foundation of the Arya Samaj on April 10th, 1875 was the culmination of the religious thought and activities of Swami Dayananda Saraswati. It was originally founded at Bombay in 1875, but was revised at Lahore in 1877, when its principles received their final shape and its constitution was finally settled. The most striking feature in connection with the Arya Samaj, which makes it at once the most powerful and the most influential of all reform movements in the country, is its complete and wonderful organization. Every Arya Samajist is a unit in itself. Generally, there is one in every city or villages which has come under its influence, but in some cities there are more than one, either on account of the distance separating the different parts of the same city or an account of some slight difference in principle.

Dayanand's opposition to the establishment of Arya Samaj on the basis of any cult of personality was remarkable. He was an egalitarian. He wanted that the Arya Samaj should be established on the principles of equality, with no difference of caste, position, learning etc. In the eyes of the society everyone should be regarded as equal. He never wanted to be treated as different from the poor and the non-privileged. He told the members of the Bombay Arya Samaj that his picture was not to be hung up in the hall. At Lahore, he once entered the Samaj when 'Upasana' or prayer was being offered. All stood up to show him respect, Swamiji exhorted the audience for stand up at the time of "Upasana". Dayanand's

main object for founding the Arya Samaj was to organise a society which would devote itself to bettering and raising mankind specially the Hindu community. Here 'Samaj' means a society and 'Arya' is an epithet meaning 'noble' i.e. a society of the noble. He wanted to regenerate India and also the World. He required members to the Arya Samaj to believe in one God. He opined to read the Veda and to recite the same for others.

Major Principles of the Arya Samaj: -

The principles to which every Arya is required to subscribe when he applies for membership, the only authoritative exposition of its beliefs and doctrines. Which was as follows: -

- ❖ God is the primary cause of all true knowledge and of everything known by its means.
- ❖ God is all truth, all pervading, omniscient, imperishable, immortal, exempt from fear, eternal, holy and the cause of the Universe. To him alone worship is due.
- ❖ The Vedas are the books of true knowledge and it is the paramount duty of every Arya to read or hear the Vedas and also to teach the same for others.
- ❖ An Arya should always be ready to accept truth and to renounce untruth.
- ❖ All actions must confirm to virtue, i.e. should be performed after a thorough consideration of right and wrong.
- ❖ The primary object of the Samaj is to benefit the whole world, viz., by improving the physical, spiritual and social condition of mankind.
- ❖ All ought to be treated with love, justice and with due regards to their merits.
- ❖ Ignorance must be dispelled and knowledge diffused.

Title of The Project: -

Thus, from the foregoing discussion it is now clear that the 19th century was a glorious period regarding socio-cultural upliftment of Indian society. Simultaneously, the reformist leader tried to upgrading the society through the development of education system. Which had a deepest influence on the then contemporary society as well as our present education system. In view of the importance of the scenario, the investigator, selected the following problem for his present study- "**A Study On Educational Contribution of the Arya Samaj in India.**"

Objectives of The Study: -

The major objectives of the study are as follows: -

- ❖ To define the philosophical and educational ideas and visions of Dayanand Saraswati as well as the Arya Samaj.
- ❖ To find the prime motives that impelled the socio- religious reform movements and leaders to strengthened indigenous education.
- ❖ To reconstruct and evaluate the contributions of Maharashi Dayanand to education in his respective region of operation and to Indian education in general.
- ❖ To highlight about the services of Arya Samaj in India with special reference to their social reforms.
- ❖ To evaluate the services of the Arya Samajist's especially in the field of female education.
- ❖ To examine the social renovation activities of Arya Samaj movement.
- ❖ To evaluate the services of Arya Samajist's in the development of Indian traditional cultural heritage.
- ❖ To find out as to what extent the political situations of India were influential in the reforms and educational activities of the Arya Samaj.
- ❖ To analyse the significance and impact of the ideas and works of the Arya Samaj movements in present context.

Research Questions: -

To achieving the above mentioned objective the researcher determines the followings as his research questions, which will be highlighted throughout the work.

- ❖ What was the condition of Indian society in 19th century?
- ❖ On what perspective the Arya Samaj was established?
- ❖ What was the main philosophical basis of Dayanand and the Arya Samaj?
- ❖ What was the novelty of the Arya Samaj movements?
- ❖ What was the educational views of Maharashi Dayanand?
- ❖ Why they took their actions in the field of education?
- ❖ What was the role of Arya Samaj regarding social reforms in pre- independence period?
- ❖ Have their any contribution period? on woman education in colonial
- ❖ What was the main strategy of the Arya Samaj to imparting education?
- ❖ How the Arya Samaj movements inculcated value based education in Indian perspective?
- ❖ Have their any relevance in present socio economic perspective?
- ❖ How the Arya Samaj movements influenced on the present system of education in India?

Methodology of Research:

The historical research is of value in enabling us to discount the influence of the past and to face present day problems with confidence. Research in the history of education of properly directed may reinforce progressive tendencies and should consequently not be ignored in or excluded from programmes of educational research. An understanding of the historical background of education should enable the educators recognise facts, which advocated as the just discovered cure for educational ills, when in reality they are simply rejuvenated versions of ideas which found to be wanting.

The historical research involves three major steps. They are: -

- ❖ Collection of relevant data from the primary and secondary sources.
- ❖ Internal and external criticism in order to assess the validity of the data.
- ❖ Presentation of facts in a readable and most appreciable form involving problem of organisation, composition, exposition and interpretation.

The problem involved in the process of historical research makes it a somewhat difficult task. A major difficulty is delimiting the problem so that a satisfactory analysis is possible. The act of historical research involves the identification and limitation of a problem or an area of study, sometimes the formation of a hypothesis, the collection, organisation, verification, validation, analysis, selection of data, testing the hypothesis or answering questions which are appropriate for writing a research report.

Theory of knowledge: -

It is true that without knowledge there can be no freedom from bondage, but Dayanand always impress that knowledge not transformed into actions, can bear no fruit. Mind, according to him, is the sixth sense, whenever he speaks of senses, he enumerates six and not five. The knowledge which we get by the contact of ears, skin, eyes, tongue, nose and mind with sound, touch, form, taste, colour, pleasure, pain, truth, untruth etc. is perception. The word 'Indriya' which is Sanskrit equivalent of senses has a significant etymology. Indriya is that which belongs to Indra. Indra means self or soul. Senses including mind are instruments which help the self in the attainment of knowledge. Dayananda says, " the knowledge which we get by the contact of ears, skin, eyes, tongue, nose and mind with sound, touch, form taste, colour, pleasure, pain, truth, untruth etc. is perception.

The Impact of Dayanand's Philosophical Ideas On His Educational Views and Teachings:

According to Dayanand education begins in the mother's womb. A mother should, after the birth of the child and when he learns to speak, teach him to pronounce letters correctly. It is clear that the first teacher

of the child, according to Dayanand, was his mother and the important thing to be taught to the child was regard for religion and ethics. Dayanand was of the view that education should be pursued for the sake of education and not for preparing children for any public office or lucrative job. The function of education, according to him, was the development of the whole man and perfect personality so that he may be a useful and worthy citizen of his material world. To Dayanand, " Pursuit of knowledge is as necessary as pursuit of food. A fool may have food and may die simply because he has no knowledge as to how to use it." He defines knowledge in these words, knowledge consists in knowing a thing exactly as it is and science consists in knowing a thing differently from what it is.

Pranayam is an essential condition in Dayanand's scheme of education. According to him, the first 'Upanayan' ceremony should be performed at home and second in the school. Parents and teachers should teach Gayatri Mantra' to the students with its meaning and thereafter Sandhyopasana. Both boys and girls should practice Pranayam. Brahmacharya must be observed by the students. Character building or righteous living, according to him, is the be all and end of all reading and reciting, studying, teaching and preaching. The knowledge has an essential place in the process of education. According to Dayanand, true knowledge is something more than mere imparting a learning of facts, as it relevant to situations of life.

The Aspects of Dayananda's Educational Ideas:

❖ Aims of Education:

It is necessary for a system of education to have a well-defined aim, because without an end or ideal education cannot have that point or force which it can have in the presence of a clear cut aim. The aim is a foreseen end gives direction to activity. The aim enables both the educator and the educator to check his educational progress, revise their methods if so needed, and to reinforce their educational effort, if and when it becomes necessary. Aim is the driving force of education as of all other pursuits. In earliest days of our race, education hardly existed as a separate activity. Systematic education in India begun when the hymns of Vedas were composed. Aryans considered the gift of education as the greatest gift. Dayananda says, " it is the highest duty of parents, tutors and relatives of adorn children with good sound education, nobility of character, refinement of manners and amiability of temper."

❖ Spiritual Development Aim:

The educational institutions had account of the noble character of the teacher. It was in such atmosphere that the young mind was nurtured. Spirituality, therefore, was a characteristic of their education. It is

really an irony of fate Indians are blindly following the path of western materialism losing our hereditary spiritual ground.

Indian Education Commission (1964-1966) rightly declares "This concept of the mingling of science and spirituality is of significance for Indian education." To sum up, we can say education should make an individual vocationally self intellectually mature, socially efficient, culturally rational, virtuous and spiritually advanced. Although the other aims looked after, the spiritual aim is totally absent. It is in this that Dayanand's emphasis on spiritual aim needs to be reiterated.

❖ **Cultural Aims of Education:**

Education is intended only to initiate the pupil into that of his community and enable him to live according to its standards. Without culture, man is not better than an animal. Man's progress till now is revealed through his culture. It is in that that Dayanand drew the attention of the people of India to the Vedic phase of Indian culture.

❖ **Character Formation Aim:**

Character building was the chief aim of education in the Vedic and Brahmanic period. Dayanand in Satyarth Prakash says mere intellectual attainments are of no worth, if the person is devoid of moral feeling and character. The concept of character varies according to the ideals that are put before us, and the meaning also differs time to time and place to place. The present education prepares a student for certain vocations and vocationalism cuts root of character.

Dayanand was of the view that constructive criticism leads to formation of good character. According to him, teachers should be of character, so that the students may follow them. His strongest view was that it is through direct human relationship that can lead a moral and a virtuous life. As is the teacher so taught; as is the society so will be the individual.

❖ **Knowledge as an Aim of Education:**

Knowledge to the Aryans was the supreme goal or at least a gateway towards it. This produced their scholars, best men of and profound philosophers. Intellectual and spiritual development were their chief aims of education. To them possession of knowledge and academic skills were the guarantors of good life.

❖ **Preparation for Life: As an Aim:**

Preparation for living, social efficiency, vocation or until were not explicit but implicit in the system of Aryan According to Dayanand, only those were fit to be members and organised community who learned in their school da plain living and discipline. This means that aims of educa produce citizens who were socially efficient.

As Dayanand follows Vedic spiritualism and accepts the of thought, his philosophy is idealism and his educational applied idealism emanating from spiritual monism. He st education rather than vocation. He accepts social aim b more on individual aim. To him education is primarily direction in accordance with the revealed path of Vedic.

❖ **Scheme of Studies or the Curriculum:**

Curriculum is the only means for fulfilling the aim education. So it is bound to be determined by the educational a The teacher selects those subjects of study which promise to help pupils to realise in their lives Ross says, " The curriculum include the knowledge and skills that the child requires, not only his present life as a child, but also for his future life as an adult.

The Vedic literature naturally formed the main topic of study this period. Students were required to master the principles of pro and encouraged to develop the powers of versification. The study elementary Geometry and knowledge of astronomy was also important Grammar and etymology did not trouble the students of that because they were yet to be developed.

The Rig Veda, the Yajur Veda, the Sama Veda and the Aharva Ved came into existence in later Vedic period. This specialisation of Vedic studies. The study of astronomy, geometry prosody continued to progress in this period. The development sciences of grammar and etymology started in this age and manuals on those subjects were included in the curriculum.

❖ **Teacher-Pupil Relationship:**

In addition to imparting intellectual education the teacher in ancient India had to perform several other duties as well. He was to be the spiritual father of the children. The teachers were to treat their students like their own sons. In modern times, when a students' desires to get admission to any institution, he presents himself before an unknown teacher. Money in the form of fees constitutes the primary link between the teacher and the students' Naturally such relations are not built on the foundation stone of love and faith.

In ancient Vedic period self-study was emphasised but the teacher was considered indispensable. Harmonious relation between the teacher and the pupil is a prerequisite to worthwhile learning. The distinguished characteristics of ancient Indian education is the ideal relationship between pupil and the teacher. The relationship was that of a father and son, because the pupil lived at the house of the teacher. The teacher was the spiritual and intellectual father. The relation between the students and the teacher was direct and not through any institution.

❖ **Woman Education:**

Vedic and Later Vedic Period: Woman of India had always enjoyed freedom to the highest degree. They were not only given full freedom of education but also they played a very important part in social and cultural life. In Manu Smriti it is clearly written that woman must perform the Upanayana ceremony. It was essential for girls as well as for boys. Hence woman education was compulsory there was some evidence also that there was co-education at least at the higher stage. Thus we see that woman in Vedic period were highly respected and were given very high place in the society. In the post Vedic period too, woman folk were honoured. The only difference which had occurred was that the superiority of the husband was established. In the Smriti period the circumstances changed. Girls began to be married at a very early age. This naturally checked the growth of female education, except that which girls could get at home.

Buddhist Period: Lord Buddha himself was not in favour of woman education. As a religious leader his main aim of life was to spread truth and ahimsa. At a later stage woman were allowed to join the monasteries. The effect of woman education during this period was only on the nobility and on the high families. Moreover, the custom of child marriage also prevented the spread of female education. So at the

❖ **Religious and Moral Education:**

It is through religion, says Ross, "that the feet of the youth set on the road to those values." One of the functions of education is to perpetuate our culture, to reconstruct it in the light of needs, to produce and maintain a high degree of civilisation safeguard it against periodical lapses into barbarism. Education performs this function only if it is based on religion.

❖ **Physical Education:**

Dayanand acquired the place above from his contemporaries physically as well as intellectually and spiritually. He was a giant in body as well as in intellect, and stood head and shoulders above them, in

stature, in the built of his body and in the physical vigour, he dominated the people where ever he went. By dint of this celibacy, his body was of the greatest service to him in the gigantic task of redeeming humanity which he had undertaken.

❖ **Social Education:**

During the 18th century the Indian society had been on decline in all the spheres. The Indians were the original teachers and leaders of mankind, and has attained a very high level of civilization and culture. Their national character as regards chivalry, honour and truthfulness was unrivalled. The people who had reached the summit of spiritual glory and the pinnacle of worldly prosperity, became helplessly divided, weak and ignorant, unable to defend themselves

Interpretations On the Relevance of the Educational Ideas and Teachings of Dayanand and His Arya Samaj and Their Impact On Present Day:

In this study historical analysis has been undertaken by the researcher to discern the contributions of Arya Samaj on education. Utmost care has been taken to present the matter in an appreciable and authentic manner on the basis of available historical data. A brief study on the valuable services of the Arya Samaj in various fields of their activities are attempted as concluding part of this study. This chapter is the personal interpretation of the researcher when the analysis of the data was made.

There is a well-known proverb that history repeats itself. This is equally true in respect of social and educational ideas of great personalities like Sankaracharya, Ramanuja, Dayanand and others Here lies the importance of studying the philosophical ideas of noted personalities. Again, present is the child of the past and present leads to the future. Dayanand has left an educational and philosophical legacy behind him, which can inspire the present generations to create a bright future. This legacy or lessons of his teachings may be summarised in brief.

Revival of National Cultural Heritage Dayanand was born and nurtured in an atmosphere of glorious nationalist values and ideas based on our traditional cultural heritage. He practised and translated those cultural values in his own life and gave a clarion call to revive those ideals of ancient Vedic age. He strongly advocated Vedic revivalism. That was key note of his philosophical and educational teachings. His slogan was, 'Go back to the Vedas'.

Findings: -

Major findings of the study are as follows:

- ❖ Indian society in 18th and 19th century was covered with different types of conservatism, dogmatism and social evils.
- ❖ The rule of English East India Company and British Government growing the seeds of Indian nationalism in the minds of Indian intelligentsia.
- ❖ The sociocultural renaissance of 19th century rapidly changed the Indian situation and gave birth a large number of socio cultural reform movements under the leadership of Dayanand, Rammohun Roy, Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar, Vivekanda etc.
- ❖ The activities of the Arya Samaj was based on the principles of Vedic philosophy with a blend of modern outlook.
- ❖ The Arya Samaj movement have played a remarkable role in the socio-cultural awakening movement in colonial India.
- ❖ One of the major contributions of the Arya Samaj was in revamping of the educational scenario of the country. They firmly laid the foundation of value based education through the Vedic lines.
- ❖ The Arya Samaj wanted to stopped the spreading of western culture through patronizing an indigenous system of education.
- ❖ Educational activity of the Arya Samajist's also extended to social renovation works. They strongly protest against the evil practices of the society and wanted to bring social harmony. In this way they acted as social revolutionaries.
- ❖ (Another major contributions of the Arya Samaj movement was to upgrading the overall condition of the Indian woman's especially in the field of education.
- ❖ The activities of the Arya Samaj drew the attention of the Indian intelligentsia and inspired them towards nationalism as well as against the British imperialism.
- ❖ The legacy of the Arya Samaj movement is still existing in our country. Achievement of the D.A.V. institutions in the field of education is the burning example of that.

Conclusions:

Arya Samaj was the first reform movement to bring the nationalism in our country. Dayanand founded the Arya Samaj with a view to reconstruct the Indian nation and society and to arouse patriotism. Certainly he was a great man who sacrificed himself for this greater cause of mankind. He dominated the lives of thousands of people and his influence still continues to this day through the Arya Samaj. This great son of India struggle hard to dispel the darkness of ignorance engulfing the minds of the millions of India's sons. When the forces of disintegration are active in the country, when the very existence of Bharatvarsha, the land of philosophers, Rishis and Munis is in danger due to aggression from

neighbouring countries, or the aggression from some dogmatic and hypocritical citizen within the country, there is no need to argue that education reconstruction and national and emotional unity must be based on for education system. After his death, his followers thought that the best memorial that they could raise to him, was to establish high grade schools, colleges and Gurukulas on the ancient Vedic line for overcome the degradation of teacher student relationship. The Kangri Gurukul near Haridwar and the Brindaban Gurukul near Mathura are two notable institutions in India which are trying to put into practice up to a certain extent some of the ideals of education and the teacher taught relationship as advocated by Dayananda.

We are at present generally complaint that the low level of intellectual development reached by our students what else can we expect when a wide gulf between the teacher and the pupils are staying in the system. We know that secret of success...

Dayanand advocated for separate education for boys' and girls'. He was deadly against coeducation. It is very difficult to agree with this view of Dayananda in present scenario. Because, a present co-education getting so popular. But at the same time, the deterioration of education, character, discipline in coeducational institutions certainly calls for serious consideration of the principle advocated by Dayananda. Though it is not possible to arrange separate education for men and woman in the field of high education or university education.

Dayanand's views on education was in the truest sense of the term a democratic one. His services to humanity recognised him a world teacher, which he deserves and which properly belongs him.

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